

Clinician feedback on the design features of an AI tool to identify Fabry disease

Vera Onongaya¹, Matthew Ploszajski²[0000-0001-6099-1561], Suraj Ramchand², Duncan Cole¹ and Xianghua Xie²[0000-0002-2701-8660]

¹ Cardiff University, Cardiff, CF10 3AT, UK

² Swansea University, Singleton Park, Swansea, SA2 8PP, UK
onongayav@cardiff.ac.uk

Abstract. This paper presents feedback from a focus group of cardiologists (n=6) regarding an AI tool to assist in the identification of Fabry disease. The key feedback on the features, explainability and its role in clinical workflow are explored.

Keywords: Fabry Disease, Medical AI, Medical Human-Computer Interaction.

1 Background

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly being deployed in clinical settings to assist clinicians with identifying diseases, develop new treatments, process test results and more besides. However, many medical AI systems have struggled to find acceptance in clinical practice due to a lack of trust from clinicians and patients^[1]. A lack of explainability, poor integration with workflows and minimal regulatory approval^[2] have all been reported as common reasons for distrust from users.

Fabry disease (FD) is a rare inherited metabolic condition, characterised by a broad range of symptoms, including chronic pain, fatigue, clouded vision and a heightened risk of heart attack and stroke. Detection of FD is challenging, with the disease commonly misdiagnosed as hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM). Delays in diagnosis can have a detrimental impact on the individual's overall well-being as well as incur excessive costs for treatment.

This study is part of an ongoing project to develop an AI tool to support clinicians to quickly identify FD from routine cardiology investigations. Here we present the feedback from a focus group of cardiologists at The University Hospital of Wales (UHW), Cardiff who were demonstrated a prototype version of the tool, given the opportunity to ask questions of the research team and suggests future design priorities.

2 Study Design

The AI4Fabry Platform. The platform under investigation is a prototype online web-tool entitled AI4Fabry (<https://ai4fabry.streamlit.app/>). The web-tool has fields where information can be entered on a patient's demographic information, medical history

and the outcome of any cardiology investigations (currently limited to echo cardiogram, electro-cardiography and 24-hour holter monitor). The web-tool contains a pre-trained model that provides a prediction on the likelihood that a patient has FD on a scale of 0-1. For a full description of how the model was trained, please see Ramchand, et al.^[3]. At present, the web-tool has only been trained to recognise FD or HCM.

To enhance the explainability of the web-tool's prediction, a user can open graphs that display the extent to which the features in the data contributed to the prediction, derived from a combination of the XGBoost method's split gain, cover and frequency of use functions. A graph also explains the SHAP values^[4] to display the extent to which a patient's data features contributed towards a FD or HCM prediction specifically.

Furthermore, the web-tool contains a language model that can be interrogated to explain the model's decision in plain language, highlighting the most relevant features and how they relate to FD or HCM.

User Centered Design. The prototype was presented to clinicians via a semi-structured group discussion. Clinicians were recruited from UHW. A total of six cardiologists participated, comprising of 3 consultants and 3 junior doctors. The discussion occurred in a private room at the hospital and lasted approximately 30 minutes. This was facilitated by the author using a Mentimeter presentation with videos and photos of the prototype. Participants were encouraged to verbally share their views, and the option to anonymously post their views via the presentation was made available.

The discussion was transcribed (non-verbatim) by the facilitator for thematic analysis. A deductive approach to analysis was undertaken where opinions were linked to three preconceived themes: features (interface layout, data input, etc), explainability (how well does the AI-tool provide a clear reason on output) and workflow (the integration of this tool in a clinician's workflow).

3 Key Findings

The feedback from the doctors on the pre-conceived themes was as follows:

Tool features. The strongest feedback from all participants was that manual inputting of data was too time-consuming and would prevent them from using the tool. The consultants reported that before seeing the interface they would like to see the probability of a patient having FD, for example, in a patient with unexplained left ventricular hypertrophy. They also felt that forecasting features to detect early cardiac involvement would be a valuable feature as this would influence the patient's management.

Explainability. The consultants did not think that they would use the chatbot feature to interrogate the data, as they felt that it was too polite and relied too heavily to stock "template" responses to feel trustworthy. The junior doctors reported that the chatbot language and the feature importance graphs were clear, but that the SHAP values graph should be re-named, as this is not a familiar term for a clinical audience.

Workflow. The consultants did not think that they would use the tool, as they felt that their expertise to identify suspected FD would not need to be confirmed with an AI tool and they would not trust it if it contradicted them. However, the junior doctors reported that they would find this tool useful in a secondary care setting if they are less familiar

with the signs of FD as a prompt for something to consider. The consultants also suggested that a tool such as this could have a role in primary care settings to screen routine ECG scans in GP settings. They also felt that including information on FD's other symptom profiles in neurology and renal settings would be useful.

4 Conclusions

The prototype was received positively with most clinicians approving of the simple layout. However, the inputting of secondary care data was a major deterrent to using this tool due to time-constraints in practice, a limitation not currently reported in the medical AI literature. Future designs of the tool will integrate this feedback by including a feature to automatically populate input values from clinical reports to greatly reduce the time to receive a prediction.

The feature importance table was interpretable by the clinicians and was effective in explaining the tool's prediction. Nonetheless, clinicians did not see themselves interacting with the language model despite its ability to explain the AI output further.

The consultants could not perceive the integration of this tool in their workflow, although, the junior doctors did. The junior doctors would prefer to use this tool once receiving a referral from primary care (rather than later in their workflow). Few studies investigate the integration of AI diagnostic tools into existing clinical workflows: Yang, et al. (2019)^[5] promotes the integration of the system into existing electronic systems for ease of access, however, no study explores when a clinician should use this tool.

Although the discussion included consultants and junior doctors of equal number, the consultants dominated the conversation despite attempts to allow anonymous sharing of opinions via an online poll system. Moreover, the group discussion format prevents an in-depth analysis of opinions and introduces bias from others. Individual interviews exploring explainability and workflow should be conducted with junior doctors as they are most likely to benefit/use this tool in secondary care.

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